

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICS IN SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT.

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Annotation: *Man is always in a complex interaction with the world around him. This is a study of interactions. Due to this, the nature around us is studied using a number of sciences. Among these sciences, physics occupies an important place.*

Key words: *Physics, astronomy, theoretically, conducted, radio*

The achievements of physics in the study of the universe began to be seen in the middle of the twentieth century. In this period, technology has reached a new stage of its development rose. In developed countries, production has begun to move to full mechanization and automation. Due to the development of some industries, human labor was divided into non-manual labor.

Physics as a science emerged as a result of the demands of social production. The achievements of physics in the early stages of human social development are great. His discoveries in electromagnetic phenomena led to the development of modern energy, automation, and radio communications.

The development of physics is inextricably linked with other sciences. The development of electron microscopy and X-ray structural devices has helped to study the structure of crystals and complex biological structures.

Due to advances in atomic nuclei and particle physics, neutrino astronomy is currently being developed. Neutrino astronomy provides scientists with information about processes in the depths of cosmic names, such as in the solar plexus, allowing them to be studied.

The emergence of molecular biology and genetics has led to development in biology. Molecular biology and genetics study life in the smallest particles of a living organism - molecules. Molecular biology derives its basic tools and methods of detecting, separating, and studying its objects from physics. It uses electron and praton microscopes, X-ray structure analysis, labeled atoms and so on.

The role of modern physics in the development of a number of natural sciences, such as chemistry, geology, oceanology, medicine, is extremely important. Extensive possibilities of obtaining radioactive isotopes, laser beams are of great scientific help to medical professionals.

Development in the field of materials science is associated with the creation and introduction into production of artificial materials technology. Along with the development of chemistry in the creation of such materials with predetermined properties with new properties, physical methods of exposure to matter (electron, ion and laser beam bundles, ultra-strong magnetic fields, ultra-high pressure and temperatures, ultrasound, etc.) are playing an increasingly important role.

Development in energy has been linked to the transition from fossil fuel-fired thermal power plants to nuclear power plants. Based on the achievements of physics, man acquired atomic energy.

Research in the field of solid state physics has led to the development of radio engineering, communication technology, high-speed computing technology, and the development of fast-growing semiconductor technology. To date, a generation of electronic computers with vacuum lamps, semiconductors and integrated circuits has been created in physics laboratories. The use of lasers and the development of holography based on them create new opportunities for further improvement of electronic computing techniques.

It should be noted that modern technology and technology, in turn, influences the development of physics. For example, in nuclear physics, a flow of particles of large enough energy is required to conduct research. Such energetic particles could be obtained in powerful accelerators created only due to the high level of technology.

In applied physics, it is necessary to calculate some parameters using complex formulas to theoretically substantiate the experimental results. The service of modern computers is invaluable.

After the independence of the Republic, great attention is paid to the development of science. The contribution of our compatriot scientists to the development of physics and its practical application is great. Regular research in Uzbekistan was established in 1949 at the Institute of Physics and Technology. After the establishment of the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1956 on the initiative of academicians IV Kurchatov, UO Oripov and SA Azimov, it became possible to further expand this research. Currently, research is being conducted in the field of nuclear spectroscopy and nuclear structure, nuclear reactions, quantum field theory, elementary particle physics, relativistic nuclear physics and other areas.

There is a lot of work being done in Uzbekistan in the field of high energy physics. Such research is being conducted at the Institute of Physics and Technology of the Physics-Sun Production Association, the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University.

In conclusion, physics is the basis of the development of modern science and technology. Therefore, in the current fields of physics, such as discoveries in atomic and nuclear physics, the use of nuclear energy, modern televisions and computers, the exploration and practical use of space, the reception of radio and television broadcasts from anywhere in the world, wireless it is necessary to have a brief knowledge and imagination about the creation of means of speech.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. M.H Olmasova. Physics Optics, atomic and nuclear physics. Textbook for academic lyceums / edited by BMMirzahmedov. - T .: Cholpon Publishing House, 2007.
2. N.M Shaxmayev, SN Shaxmayev, D.Sh. Shodiyev. Physics. Electromagnetic waves Physics of the twentieth century Fundamentals of molecular physics and thermodynamics. Textbook for 11th grade of high school. - T .: "Teacher", 2004.
3. N.Sh. Turdiyev [and others]. Physics. Textbook for students of 11th grade of secondary education and secondary special, vocational education institutions. - T .: Niso Polygraph Publishing House, 2018